

Background & Objectives

The **torsion beam** in the **twist beam axle** plays a vital role in transferring forces and moments between the wheels and vehicle body, ensuring roll stability and safety. **Traditionally made of high-strength steel**, torsion beams can be enhanced with **fiber-reinforced polymer composites**, offering **superior strength, stiffness, manufacturability, and corrosion resistance**. **Hybrid composites**, combining synthetic and natural fibers, provide a promising solution to **reduce mass and carbon footprint** while **maintaining mechanical performance** comparable to purely synthetic composites.

Objectives

- Analyze the **elastic mechanical behavior** of hemp fiber-reinforced epoxy (HFRE), glass fiber-reinforced epoxy (GFRE), and two **hybrid intra-ply configurations (H0G90 and H90G0)** to evaluate their potential for **improving structural performance**.
- Investigate the performance of **quasi-isotropic plain-woven hybrid hemp/glass fiber-reinforced composites** in torsion beams, focusing on **torsional, vertical, and longitudinal stiffness** using **multiscale modeling**.

Stacking Sequence Design for Torsion Beam Modeling

Table 1: Number of plies in various stacking sequences and the resulting thickness and mass of each torsion beam model with hemp fiber content in %.

Model	No. of plies	Thickness (mm)	Mass (kg)	Hemp fiber content (%)
Steel_U-shape	-	6.0	8.26	-
GFRE	20	8.0	3.62	-
HFRE	40	16.0	4.84	100
Hybrid_H/G	26	10.4	3.87	53.8
H0G90	30	12.0	4.54	46.4
H90G0	28	11.2	4.24	46.4
H90G0 & HFRE(Mid)	32	12.8	4.36	73.2

Note: The **thickness and number of plies** in each composite stacking sequence (**0.4 mm/ply**) are based on the **torsional stiffness of the baseline steel U-shaped torsion beam**.

Methods

Validation of Elastic Properties of GFRE and HFRE compared to Hybrid Intra-ply Models

Torsion Beam Analysis

Conclusions

- All composite torsion beams showed **1.74 to 2.2 times higher specific torsional stiffness (K_T)** than the baseline steel beam, with **GFRE achieving the highest K_T** . The **hybrid inter-ply model (H/G)** performed similarly to GFRE, with only a **4.8% reduction in stiffness**.
- The **GFRE model had the highest specific vertical bending stiffness (K_V)**, while the **hybrid composite models showed a 3.50 to 4.57 times improvement in K_V** over the steel baseline.
- Hybrid intra-ply configurations, especially **H90G0**, demonstrated **superior mechanical properties** due to **optimal fiber alignment**, with the **H90G0 & HFRE(Mid) model** combining the benefits of both **inter- and intra-ply hybridization** and a **high hemp fiber content (73.2%)**. However, the hybrid models showed limited effectiveness under longitudinal loading, indicating their **suitability for torsional and bending applications**.

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